

CRIMINAL PROCEDURAL FORM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6390193>

Annotation. The thesis analyzes the theoretical and legal aspects of criminal procedural forms of ensuring individual rights in criminal proceedings.

Keywords: person, form, guarantee, crime, criminal procedure, investigation.

One of the important institutions of criminal procedure is the forms of criminal procedure. A number of scientific studies have been conducted by procedural scholars in this category, and theoretical rules have been developed in this regard.

In particular, the conditions specified in the law, the sequence of formalization of criminal proceedings, the emergence, change or termination of the relevant legal relationship is called a form of criminal procedure [1].

The content of the concept of procedural forms constitutes the legal procedures, conditions and guarantees provided for in the rules of criminal procedure [2].

Criminal procedural forms are a system of norms regulating in a certain sequence the procedure for making decisions on the relations arising in connection with the activities of the subjects of criminal proceedings and the conditions for their reconsideration "[3].

Also, the criminal-procedural form is a set of legal procedures, conditions and guarantees enshrined in law that ensure the solution of the tasks of the criminal procedure [4].

The criminal-procedural form is a criminal procedure and its separate stages, the structure of the conditions of which is enshrined in criminal-procedural law, the sequence and order of execution of procedural actions and registration in legal documents. The characteristics of the criminal-procedural form are: 1) the superiority of the principle of transparency over dispositiveness in the solution of the problem and the choice of methods of behavior of the participants in the process; 2) the actions of the participants in the process are provided by the state coercive measures; 3) the nature of the coercion depends on the social risk of the crime committed; 4) the existence of a preliminary

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investigation institute; 5) that justice is the only way to prosecute and punish the guilty or acquit an innocent person; 6) the existence of an institution to protect the rights and legitimate interests of the suspect, accused, defendant [5].

It is expedient to connect the concept of criminal procedural forms with the procedures for recording in procedural documents the actions performed in criminal proceedings.

An important component of the procedural form is the procedural documents of the procedural form defined in the JPK. In them, the bodies of inquiry, the investigator, the prosecutor, the judge or the court, within the limits of their authority, answer questions arising in the criminal case in the manner prescribed by law [6].

Based on the above, the inquiry, preliminary investigation, prosecution and prosecution of criminal cases in the manner prescribed by law, investigation, assignment of criminal case materials to the court, their content, verification of legality, validity and fairness of judgments, rulings and decisions, as well as special attention should be paid to ensuring the rights of the individual in the registration of procedural activities in the procedural documents on appeals for the execution of court decisions.

The requirement of unconditional adherence to a procedural form cannot be viewed as mere formality. Procedural form is an important guarantee of the legality and validity of criminal procedural documents, the accuracy of judicial repression, the high level of socio-educational significance of criminal proceedings, the full protection of the rights and legitimate interests of the individual in criminal proceedings. If we pay attention to the forms of criminal procedure in force, we will see that each form is in accordance with the law. For example, the condition for instituting criminal proceedings is the existence of its grounds and reasons; the condition for involving a person in the case as a defendant is the availability of sufficient material and procedural grounds; the condition for passing a guilty verdict is that the defendant's guilt is unconditionally proven in court, and so on [7].

The issues of ensuring the rights of the individual in relation to the priority of the principle of transparency in resolving the issue and choosing the methods of behavior of the participants in the process can be interpreted as follows.

In this case, we can cite Article 19 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to these norms, except in some cases, the public hearing of criminal cases, ie public hearings in court, means a trial in

which the case is heard in the presence of citizens of legal age and wishing to appear in court.

Transparency in court allows for a more effective and comprehensive solution to the task of educating citizens in the spirit of respect for the law and intolerance of lawlessness, while ensuring the constant control of the judiciary by the public [8].

In addition, the openness of the proceedings allows the parties to make a lawful decision and ensure the rights of the individual during the pre-trial proceedings, ie during the pre-trial investigation and the investigation of the criminal case.

Procedural coercive measures and protection of individual rights. It should be noted that coercive procedural measures are, according to criminal procedure law, a means of restricting the rights of an individual at certain stages of the criminal process.

However, these procedural coercive measures are applied in the interests of society and the state.

In this case, justice is guaranteed and the rights of the individual are guaranteed as a result of the application of procedural coercive measures to prevent the further criminal activity of the suspect or accused and to ensure the execution of the sentence in cases where the participant in the criminal proceedings obstructs the investigation or failure to perform the duties imposed on him.

In particular, detention is a short-term imprisonment of a suspect in order to prevent him from engaging in criminal activity, escape, concealment or destruction of evidence. Detention can be carried out both before and after the initiation of a criminal case[9].

It is clear from this coercive procedural measure that the application of this measure in order to prevent concealment or destruction of evidence containing factual information about the commission of the crime, while ensuring the rights and legitimate interests of the victim, is important in quality and lawful resolution of the case.

Of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with Article 238, the inquiry officer, investigator, prosecutor, court, in addition to the grounds provided for in Article 236 of this Code, shall determine the gravity of the offense, the identity of the accused, type of occupation, age, health, marital status and other circumstances. takes into account.

The circumstances that are taken into account by the competent authorities in the selection of precautionary measures are important in ensuring the rights of the individual at the stage of application of precautionary measures in criminal proceedings.

For example, Article 249 of the Code of Criminal Procedure stipulates that the amount of bail may not be less than twenty times the basic amount. In this case, the imposition of this measure of restraint on the accused or defendant, depending on the gravity of the crime committed by the investigator or judge, is one of the measures to ensure the rights of these persons.

That is, according to this article, the inquiry officer, investigator, prosecutor or court, who chose this measure, determines the gravity of the accusation, taking into account the identity of the suspect, accused, defendant and mortgagor, the mortgagor's property status and his relationship with the suspect, accused, defendant.

Justice is the only way to prosecute and punish a guilty person or acquit an innocent person. According to Article 12 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, justice in criminal cases is administered only by a court.

Also, in some sources, the concept of "justice" - a fair, lawful resolution of issues related to crimes and civil cases[10].

The definition of "justice" shows that in criminal proceedings, it is important that cases are resolved within the law.

Article 82 of the Code of Criminal Procedure requires that the following be proved in order to pass a conviction:

- 1) the object of the crime; the nature and extent of the damage caused by the crime, the circumstances characterizing the identity of the victim;
- 2) time, place, method of the crime, as well as other cases specified in the Criminal Code; the causal link between the act and the socially dangerous consequences that occurred;
- 3) the crime was committed by this person;
- 4) whether the crime was committed with direct or indirect intent or as a result of negligence or self-belief, the causes and purposes of the crime;
- 5) circumstances characterizing the identity of the accused, defendant [11].

Also, according to Article 83 of this Code, the defendant is found not guilty in the following cases and must be rehabilitated:

- 1) no criminal incident has occurred in the case where the trial was held;
- 2) his act does not contain criminal elements;

3) he is not involved in the crime committed.

From the above-mentioned norms, it can be concluded that in the consideration of cases in the courts, as one of the directions of ensuring the rights of the individual, a "fair trial" is achieved through a fair, lawful consideration of cases. In this case, justice serves as the only way to prosecute and punish the guilty or acquit the innocent.

Institute for the Protection of the Rights and Legal Interests of Suspects, Accused, and Defendants. It is one of the important institutions of criminal procedural forms in ensuring the rights of the individual in criminal proceedings.

According to Article 24 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, a suspect, accused and defendant have the right to defense. The right to defense is ensured by the obligation of the inquiry officer, investigator, prosecutor, court to explain to the suspect, accused and defendant his rights and to take measures to ensure that he has a real opportunity to use all means and methods provided by law to protect himself from charges[12].

The right of defense of the suspect, the accused is a set of procedural possibilities (means and methods) provided to him by law to deny the accusation, guilt or mitigation of liability and punishment. The right of defense of the suspect or accused is directly derived from the norms of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which guarantees personal freedom and inviolability to everyone [13].

According to the decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On judicial practice in the application of the law on the protection of the suspect and the accused", an important guarantee of the protection of the suspect, the accused - until proven guilty in strict adherence to the principle of the presumption of innocence enshrined in the Constitution that one should not be found guilty until proven guilty.

In conclusion, it should be noted that on the basis of the lawful, reasonable and fair resolution of actions in criminal proceedings, their registration in procedural documents, along with the rights of the individual in the process, is important in ensuring justice.

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